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Impact of Test Anxiety on the Academic Performance of Undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of test anxiety on the academic performance of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the investigation. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 30,583 undergraduates, from which a sample of 380 students was selected using Glenn's (1994) formula. Data were collected using a structured researcher-developed instrument titled "Test Anxiety and Academic Performance Questionnaire (TAAPQ)," comprising 15 items structured on a modified four-point Likert scale. A pilot study was conducted and the reliability analysis done using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient yield a score of .758 which was considered sufficient. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while chi-square (X^2) goodness-of-fit was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that test anxiety significantly impacts academic motivation, academic achievement, and academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in the institution. The study concluded that test anxiety shapes the learning experiences and academic outcomes of students by undermining motivation, diminishing academic performance, and weakening confidence in academic abilities. The study recommended, among others, that the university should implement structured cognitive-behavioural and psychoeducational interventions to help students manage anxiety-inducing thoughts, as well as integrate motivation-enhancing strategies such as mentorship, stress-management workshops, and motivational counselling into student support services.

Keywords: Test Anxiety, Academic Performance, Academic Motivation, Academic Achievement, and Academic Self-Efficacy

INTRODUCTION

Across the world, academic performance remains a major benchmark for assessing the quality and effectiveness of education at all levels. It reflects how well students achieve learning objectives and demonstrate intellectual competence through grades, test scores, and scholarly achievements (Alkan & Arslan, 2019). Globally, educators and policymakers are increasingly concerned about the rising trend of poor academic performance among university students. In many developed countries, including the United States and the United Kingdom, studies have shown that a growing number of undergraduates struggle to meet academic expectations due to emotional distress, lack of motivation, and particularly, high levels of test anxiety (Thomas, Cassady, & Finch, 2020).

In Africa, the situation appears even more concerning. Many African universities continue to record low academic performance despite increased access to higher education and improved teaching infrastructure.

Factors such as poor study habits, inadequate student support services, and psychological stressors have been identified as major contributors (Mensah & Kuranchie, 2021). Test anxiety, in particular, has emerged as a pervasive issue among African undergraduates, manifesting as excessive worry, tension, and loss of concentration during examinations. These symptoms often lead to lower grades, reduced self-confidence, and a gradual decline in academic motivation (Olanrewaju & Adejumo, 2020). In Nigeria, the problem of poor academic performance among undergraduates has drawn the attention of educational stakeholders. Despite the efforts of universities to enhance teaching methods and provide supportive learning environments, a significant proportion of students continue to perform below expectations (Okoiye & Popoola, 2021). Test anxiety has been identified as one of the psychological barriers impeding academic success, as many students experience fear, nervousness, and self-doubt during examinations (Eze, 2019). Such emotional disturbances can diminish students' ability to think clearly, recall information, and apply knowledge effectively, resulting in academic outcomes that do not reflect their true potential.

Academic performance refers to the measurable outcomes of a student's learning efforts, typically indicated by grades, test scores, and overall academic achievement (Alkan & Arslan, 2019). It serves as an important indicator of how effectively educational goals are being achieved at both individual and institutional levels. In universities, academic performance not only reflects students' intellectual growth but also determines their progression, employability, and contribution to national development. However, in recent years, there has been growing concern over the persistent decline in the academic performance of undergraduates in Nigerian universities. Many students who appear to possess the intellectual capacity to excel often perform below expectations, raising questions about the underlying causes of this worrying trend (Okoiye & Popoola, 2021).

Several factors have been identified as contributors to low academic performance among students, including poor study habits, inadequate learning resources, overcrowded classrooms, and limited motivation (Adeyemo, 2020). However, beyond these structural and environmental factors lies a significant psychological dimension that has been found to influence academic performance. It is test anxiety. Test anxiety is a psychological condition characterized by excessive worry, fear, or nervousness before and during examinations, which can disrupt concentration, memory, and reasoning abilities (Putwain & Symes, 2018). When anxiety levels exceed a manageable threshold, they tend to interfere with students' ability to recall learned information, leading to underperformance despite adequate preparation (Eze, 2019).

Studies have shown that test anxiety is one of the most pervasive emotional challenges affecting students in higher institutions. According to Okon and Ibeneme (2022), students with high levels of test anxiety often experience physiological symptoms such as rapid heartbeat, sweating, and restlessness, alongside cognitive symptoms like negative self-talk and fear of failure. These symptoms collectively undermine confidence, focus, and performance. Similarly, Adegboyega and Ogunyemi (2021) found that test anxiety significantly reduces academic motivation and academic self-efficacy, which are key predictors of success in higher education.

Academic motivation refers to the internal drive, desire, or intention that prompts students to engage in learning activities and persist in achieving academic goals. It is the force that directs and sustains learners' behaviour toward success in their studies (Ryan & Deci, 2020). According to Schunk, Pintrich, and Meece (2018), motivation in academic settings involves both intrinsic factors, such as personal interest and enjoyment of learning, and extrinsic factors, such as grades, recognition, or future career prospects. When students are adequately motivated, they tend to demonstrate higher levels of effort, persistence, and engagement, which may contribute to better academic outcomes.

In the university, academic motivation plays a crucial role in shaping how students approach their studies, respond to challenges, and sustain focus in the face of academic pressure. Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (2017) suggests that motivation arises from the fulfilment of three basic psychological needs. When these needs are met, students are more likely to engage in learning willingly and effectively. Conversely, when these needs are undermined by external pressures or emotional

barriers, such as fear of failure, students may lose interest, experience reduced persistence, and show declining performance. A growing body of research indicates that test anxiety might be one of the factors that interfere with students' academic motivation. According to Hammad and Musa (2021), students who experience high levels of test anxiety often report decreased motivation to study, primarily because anxiety tends to shift their focus from learning to fear of poor performance. Similarly, Adegboyega and Ogunyemi (2021) found that test-anxious students frequently struggle with low confidence and avoidance behaviours, which could hinder their intrinsic motivation to learn. In such cases, the anticipation of evaluation may create a cycle of worry and disengagement that gradually erodes students' willingness to put in the required academic effort.

Academic achievement generally refers to the extent to which a student has attained specific educational goals within a given academic setting, often measured through grades, test scores, and other indicators of learning outcomes (Owolabi & Ajiboye, 2020). It is an important benchmark for assessing the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes and reflects how well students apply acquired knowledge and skills to academic tasks (Alhassan, 2019). In higher education, academic achievement is not only a measure of intellectual competence but also a determinant of future opportunities, such as employment, scholarships, and postgraduate advancement (Nwosu & Okechukwu, 2022). However, academic achievement among undergraduates appears to fluctuate due to a variety of academic, environmental, and psychological factors. One such psychological factor that could influence academic achievement is test anxiety. Studies have suggested that when students experience heightened anxiety before or during examinations, their ability to concentrate, recall information, and think critically may be impaired, resulting in reduced performance levels (Afolayan, Adedaja, & Olaniyi, 2021). Similarly, Opara and Nnamdi (2023) observed that students with high test anxiety tend to perform below their actual ability, even when adequately prepared, as anxiety may distort attention and cognitive processing during tests. Test anxiety might therefore act as an internal barrier that limits the demonstration of students' true academic potential affecting even their academic self-efficacy.

Academic self-efficacy refers to a student's belief in their ability to successfully perform academic tasks and achieve desired educational outcomes (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020). It reflects an individual's confidence in managing learning challenges, completing assignments, and succeeding in tests or examinations. Students with high academic self-efficacy are often more motivated, persistent, and resilient in the face of academic difficulties, while those with low self-efficacy may doubt their abilities and easily become discouraged (Honicke & Broadbent, 2016). In higher education, academic self-efficacy has been identified as a crucial determinant of performance, influencing how students approach learning tasks and cope with academic pressures (Usher & Pajares, 2019).

However, research suggests that test anxiety might play a moderating or even inverse role in this relationship. Students who experience high levels of test anxiety may begin to question their competence, thereby reducing their self-efficacy beliefs (Putwain & Symes, 2018). Conversely, students with strong self-efficacy might perceive examinations as challenges rather than threats, which could help to minimize anxiety and its negative impact on performance. Adegboyega and Ogunyemi (2021) note that low self-efficacy beliefs tend to magnify the effects of test anxiety, making students more vulnerable to stress and cognitive interference during examinations. Hence, within the academic context of Rivers State University, it might be important to consider how varying levels of self-efficacy among undergraduates could interact with test anxiety to influence academic motivation and achievement.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, concerns have continued to grow over the declining academic performance of undergraduates in many Nigerian universities, including Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Despite efforts by lecturers and the university management to improve teaching and learning outcomes, many students still struggle to perform to their full potential. One of the underlying but often overlooked factors contributing to this challenge is test anxiety. Test anxiety has become a worrisome issue among undergraduates, as it often manifests through restlessness, rapid heartbeat, loss of concentration, and even temporary memory loss during tests. In some cases, students who have studied adequately end up

performing poorly simply because they panic or lose confidence when faced with examination conditions. This situation not only affects their grades but also diminishes their motivation to study and erodes their belief in their academic abilities.

At Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, anecdotal evidence and informal observations suggest that a significant number of students experience some level of anxiety during tests and examinations. Many students have admitted to feeling tense and overwhelmed, leading to blank minds during exams, avoidance of challenging courses, or even withdrawal from academic activities. Such experiences may gradually reduce students' academic self-efficacy, lower their overall achievement, and negatively influence their motivation toward learning. If this problem is not properly understood and addressed, it could have far-reaching implications, not only for individual students but also for the university's overall academic standards and the future workforce of the society. It is therefore crucial to investigate how test anxiety affects undergraduates' academic motivation, achievement, and self-efficacy in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of test anxiety on academic performance of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the impact of test anxiety on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
2. examine the impact of test anxiety on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
3. assess the impact of test anxiety on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the impact of test anxiety on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?
2. What is the impact of test anxiety on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?
3. What is the impact of test anxiety on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
2. Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
3. Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study was the descriptive survey design. The population of this study was 30,583 undergraduates from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The sample for the study was 380 undergraduates selected using the multistage sampling procedure. The instrument for data collection in this study was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Test Anxiety and Academic Performance Questionnaire (TAAPQ). It was designed to collect relevant data for the study. The questionnaire was divided into three clusters (A, B and C), each reflecting one of the major variables of the study. Each cluster contains five (5) items, giving a total of 15 items. Cluster A elicited statements on test anxiety and academic motivation; Cluster B presented items on test anxiety and academic achievement and Cluster C elicited statements on test anxiety and academic self-efficacy. The questionnaire followed a Likert-modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements

made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options have numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Guidance and Counselling and one in Measurement and Evaluation. A pilot study was conducted and the reliability analysis done using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient yield a score of .758 which is sufficient. The data collected through questionnaires were analyzed based on each of the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. 2.50 was used as the criterion mean for decision making on the item to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The chi-square (χ^2) of goodness of fit will be used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of test anxiety on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 1: Means Scores of Impact of Test Anxiety on Academic Motivation of Undergraduates.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	I often feel anxious before examinations, and it reduces my motivation to study.	166	154	32	28	3.21	.881	Agreed
2	Fear of poor test results makes me lose interest in my academic goals.	280	72	12	16	3.62	.743	Agreed
3	I find it difficult to stay motivated when I constantly worry about upcoming tests.	236	112	22	10	3.51	.725	Agreed
4	My desire to study decreases when I remember my previous test failures.	178	160	26	16	3.32	.779	Agreed
5	When I manage test anxiety effectively, my motivation to learn increases.	190	130	40	20	3.29	.857	Agreed
Cluster Mean						3.39		Agreed

Table 1 indicated the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.39 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that test anxiety has impact on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of test anxiety on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 2: Means Scores of Impact of Test Anxiety on Academic Achievement of Undergraduates.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	I usually perform below my ability level because of test anxiety.	340	30	10	0	3.87	.409	Agreed
7	Excessive worry during tests reduces my accuracy and performance.	240	110	20	10	3.53	.717	Agreed
8	I often forget what I studied when I become anxious during examinations.	201	103	40	36	3.23	.980	Agreed
9	My test results are better when I am calm and confident.	190	170	16	4	3.44	.628	Agreed
10	Test anxiety prevents me from demonstrating my true academic potential.	216	116	28	20	3.39	.838	Agreed
Cluster Mean						3.49		Agreed

Table 2 indicated the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.49 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that test anxiety has impact on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Research Question 3: *What is the impact of test anxiety on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 3: Means Scores of Impact of Test Anxiety on Academic Self-Efficacy of Undergraduates.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	I doubt my academic ability whenever I feel anxious before tests.	157	148	0	75	3.02	1.098	Agreed
12	High test anxiety makes me lose confidence in my capacity to succeed academically.	70	229	7	74	2.78	.966	Agreed
13	I believe I can perform well even when I feel anxious about a test.	153	133	20	74	2.96	1.112	Agreed
14	Test anxiety lowers my belief in my ability to handle difficult academic tasks.	61	218	26	75	2.70	.964	Agreed
15	My academic confidence improves when I control my test anxiety.	1581	130	0	92	2.93	1.176	Agreed
Cluster Mean					2.98			Agreed

Table 3 indicated the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.98 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that test anxiety has impact on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test of Test Anxiety and Academic Motivation of Undergraduates.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	178.737	.000	Sig.
SA	166	95.0					
A	154	95.0					
D	32	95.0					
SD	28	95.0					
Total	380						

Table 4 revealed that $\chi^2 = 178.737$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that test anxiety has no significant impact on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt was therefore rejected. This implies that test anxiety has significant impact on academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis 2: Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 5: Chi-Square Test of Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement of Undergraduates.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	358.947	.000	Sig.
SA	240	95.0					
A	110	95.0					
D	20	95.0					
SD	10	95.0					
Total	380						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 358.947$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that test anxiety has no significant impact on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt was therefore rejected. This implies that test anxiety has significant impact on academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis 3: Test anxiety has no significant impact on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 6: Chi-Square Test of Test Anxiety and Academic Self-Efficacy of Undergraduates.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	281.747	.000	Sig.
SA	82	95.0					
A	234	95.0					
D	24	95.0					
SD	60	95.0					
Total	380						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 281.747$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that test anxiety has no significant impact on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt was therefore rejected. This implies that test anxiety has significant impact on academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses. The three null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding revealed that test anxiety has a significant impact on the academic motivation of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. This implies that when students experience heightened worry, tension, and fear about examinations, their intrinsic drive to study, set academic goals, and maintain interest in learning is weakened. In practical terms, test-anxious students may avoid study activities, procrastinate, or lose enthusiasm for coursework because anxiety interferes with their ability to stay focused and committed. This finding aligns with the earlier reviewed empirical evidence. For example, Eze, Nwobodo, and Onyema (2020) found that psychological pressures related to assessments significantly reduced students' engagement and study efforts in Ebonyi State, while Hamzat and Suleiman (2019) reported that anxiety levels among undergraduates in Ilorin negatively shaped their enthusiasm toward learning tasks. These studies support the conclusion that test anxiety may indeed undermine students' academic motivation, reinforcing the need for structured interventions that improve students' coping mechanisms and emotional regulation.

The second finding showed that test anxiety significantly affects the academic achievement of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. This suggests that anxious students tend to perform below their true academic potential, not necessarily because they lack ability, but because the cognitive and emotional burdens of anxiety interfere with memory recall, logical reasoning, and the

organization of ideas during tests. Undergraduates experiencing panic or mental blocks during examinations are less able to demonstrate what they have learned, resulting in lower test scores and weaker overall academic outcomes. This outcome is consistent with previously reviewed empirical works. For instance, Ibrahim and Mohammed (2020) reported that high test anxiety contributed to persistent low academic performance among undergraduates in Kaduna State, while Adeniyi and Fawole (2018) identified test-related worry as a predictor of reduced academic achievement among students in Oyo State. These findings mirror the present study's results, highlighting that test anxiety remains a critical barrier to students' academic success in university settings.

The third finding revealed that test anxiety has a significant impact on the academic self-efficacy of undergraduates in the study area. This means that when students experience continuous anxiety surrounding academic evaluations, their belief in their own ability to succeed in academic tasks tends to diminish. Students who are overwhelmed by anxious thoughts may begin to doubt their competence, feel incapable of tackling challenging subjects, or lose confidence in their capacity to prepare effectively for assessments. This finding is supported by previously reviewed empirical studies. Chukwu and Ede (2021) found that students in Imo State with high anxiety demonstrated significantly lower academic self-confidence and self-belief, while Lawal and Aremu (2019) established that test-induced stress significantly reduced students' perceived academic capability in Osun State. These earlier findings corroborate the present study by confirming that test anxiety undermines students' perceived competence and academic self-assurance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it is concluded that test anxiety shapes the learning experiences and outcomes of undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Across motivation, achievement, and self-efficacy, the study demonstrates that elevated anxiety undermines students' ability to remain engaged, perform well academically, and sustain confidence in their academic abilities. These patterns align with established research showing that anxiety affects cognitive processing, reduces persistence, and disrupts performance in evaluative contexts. Addressing test anxiety, therefore, is essential for improving academic outcomes and creating a more supportive learning environment.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The university should implement structured cognitive-behavioural and psychoeducational interventions that help students identify and manage anxiety-inducing thoughts. This aligns with findings similar to those in the abstracts where anxiety was shown to distort motivation by impairing emotional regulation and resilience. Motivation-enhancing strategies such as mentorship programmes, stress-management workshops, and motivational counselling should be incorporated into student support services.
2. The institution should integrate test-taking skills training, mock assessments, and time-management workshops into its academic support system. Evidence from the related abstracts shows that anxiety interferes with attention, memory retrieval, and overall performance in evaluative settings. Reducing cognitive overload and familiarising students with assessment procedures will help minimise anxiety-driven performance deficits.
3. Programmes that build students' confidence in their academic abilities should be strengthened, including peer-assisted learning, mastery-based learning support, and regular formative feedback from lecturers. The abstracts indicated that self-efficacy drops when anxiety overwhelms students' sense of control and competence. Enhancing students' belief in their capabilities will buffer the negative effect of anxiety and promote more adaptive academic functioning.

REFERENCES

Adegboyega, L. O., & Ogunyemi, A. O. (2021). Test anxiety, academic motivation and self-efficacy among undergraduates in Nigerian universities. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Psychology*, 20(2), 112–124.

- Adeniyi, O. A., & Fawole, I. O. (2018). Test-related worry as a predictor of academic achievement among undergraduates in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 12(2), 45–53.
- Adeyemo, D. A. (2020). Study habits and academic performance among university students in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Studies and Research*, 15(1), 73–84.
- Afolayan, J. A., Adedoja, G. O., & Olaniyi, T. A. (2021). Test anxiety and students' academic achievement in higher institutions. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 25(3), 145–156.
- Alhassan, R. K. (2019). Determinants of academic achievement among undergraduates in tertiary institutions. *International Journal of Higher Education Studies*, 9(2), 58–66.
- Alkan, N., & Arslan, S. (2019). Academic performance and its predictors in higher education settings. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 19(4), 124–138.
- Chukwu, C. E., & Ede, M. O. (2021). Influence of test anxiety on academic self-efficacy among university students in Imo State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Psychology*, 19(1), 88–97.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2017). Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness. *Guilford Press*.
- Eze, C. N. (2019). Test anxiety and academic performance among university students in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Foundations*, 13(2), 90–101.
- Eze, C. N., Nwobodo, V. C., & Onyema, J. I. (2020). Assessment-induced psychological pressure and students' academic engagement in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State. *Journal of Educational Foundations*, 14(3), 102–111.
- Hammad, M. A., & Musa, I. A. (2021). Influence of test anxiety on academic motivation among university students. *Journal of Educational Psychology and Counselling*, 6(1), 34–43.
- Hamzat, T. K., & Suleiman, R. A. (2019). Anxiety and learning enthusiasm among undergraduates in Ilorin, Nigeria. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 38(1), 67–75.
- Honicke, T., & Broadbent, J. (2016). The influence of academic self-efficacy on academic performance: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 17, 63–84.
- Ibrahim, M. A., & Mohammed, S. Y. (2020). Test anxiety and academic performance among undergraduates in Kaduna State. *Kaduna Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(2), 120–129.
- Lawal, B. O., & Aremu, A. O. (2019). Test-induced stress and perceived academic capability among university students in Osun State. *African Journal of Educational Psychology*, 11(2), 54–63.
- Mensah, F. K., & Kuranchie, A. (2021). Challenges affecting academic performance in African universities. *African Journal of Higher Education Studies*, 8(1), 21–35.
- Nwosu, K. C., & Okechukwu, E. C. (2022). Academic achievement and employability prospects among Nigerian undergraduates. *Journal of Educational Development in Africa*, 14(2), 99–110.
- Okoiye, O. E., & Popoola, B. I. (2021). Academic performance trends and psychological correlates among undergraduates in Nigerian universities. *Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 26(1), 55–68.
- Okon, E. E., & Ibeneme, O. M. (2022). Test anxiety and physiological responses among university students. *Journal of Counselling Psychology in Africa*, 10(2), 78–89.
- Olanrewaju, M. K., & Adejumo, G. O. (2020). Psychological stressors and academic outcomes among African undergraduates. *Journal of Educational Research in Africa*, 12(3), 133–142.
- Opara, C. C., & Nnamdi, I. U. (2023). Cognitive interference and academic performance: The role of test anxiety. *International Journal of Educational Psychology*, 11(1), 41–53.
- Owolabi, H. O., & Ajiboye, J. O. (2020). Academic achievement and learning outcomes in tertiary education. *Journal of Educational Measurement and Evaluation*, 6(2), 87–95.
- Putwain, D. W., & Symes, W. (2018). The impact of test anxiety on academic performance: A cognitive interference perspective. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(2), 331–353.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101860.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2020). Motivation and social cognitive theory. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 60, 101832.
- Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2018). *Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Thomas, C. L., Cassady, J. C., & Finch, W. H. (2020). Identifying severity standards on the cognitive test anxiety scale: Cut score determination and implications. *Psychological Assessment*, 32(6), 553–568.
- Usher, E. L., & Pajares, F. (2019). Sources of self-efficacy in school: Critical review of the literature and future directions. *Review of Educational Research*, 89(4), 546–581.